

Interview with Animator Tokuyuki Matsutake at the 10th Murcia Manga and Japanese Culture Convention

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In 2018, coinciding with its tenth anniversary, the Murcia Manga and Japanese Culture Fair hosted a very special guest, Tokuyuki Matsutake, an animation expert who began his career in the industry in the late 1980s. A multifaceted and highly skilled individual—having held a wide variety of roles in the animation sector from a young age—he has worked on renowned series such as *Naruto*, and learned alongside prominent professionals like artist Atsuko Nakajima, who, together with a young Matsutake, contributed her talent to the original 1989 anime adaptation of *Ranma ½*.

Tokuyuki Matsutake has also worked in video games, with his most notable collaborations being related to Namco's Tales of franchise—currently Namco Bandai—as well as other beloved series such as Persona, a subseries of Shin Megami Tensei. During the event, Matsutake donated an original work he created, witnessed by attendees including the team from CoolJapan.es, to the Murcia Regional Library to commemorate his visit.

Members of the CoolJapan.es team with Tokuyuki Matsutake —centre—

Interview with Tokuyuki Matsutake

Cool Japan: Good morning, Mr. Matsutake. To begin, we would like to ask you about your professional background. Did you always want to work in the animation industry?

Tokuyuki Matsutake: Absolutely. Since I was a child, I always wanted to work in animation.

CJ: Mr. Matsutake, we understand that you started your career as an in-betweener —drawing “dōga,” or in-between frames— for anime series based on manga. What can you tell us about your first experience working on an anime series?

TM: I started working as an in-betweener for a company, but usually you can’t begin as a full in-betweener right away. For about a month, I first had to practice every day, tracing and studying how to draw the lines, and so on. After about a month to a month and a half, I started working officially as an in-betweener. The first TV anime series I worked on was *Biriken*.

CJ: Later, you have worked on series that are also well known outside Japan. What has that experience meant for you? How did it feel to work on projects so successful both domestically and internationally?

TM: Well, it inspires me with a lot of respect and a bit of fear to work on projects that have become very famous. This is because I feel that if I make a mistake in my work, that mistake will be seen by many people. That part worries me.

CJ: How difficult is it for you to adjust your own drawing style to match that of another artist, as is required in an animated series?

Matsutake, drawing live in front of an audience during the Murcia Manga and Japanese Culture Convention.

TM: My own style is much easier for me to execute, but unfortunately, I can't use it. You can't do something in your own style in animation, and you can't employ it when working on someone else's work. You have to adapt. It's a complex and really difficult experience.

CJ: We see that you have carried out all kinds of work related to animation and design, such as storyboards, character design, key animation (“genga”), animation direction... Which position do you feel most comfortable with, and which one gives you the greatest sense of connection?

TM: I think what I'm really good at and what suits me best is doing genga, original drawings.

CJ: You have been involved in numerous multidisciplinary and multimedia projects, like video games and anime series based on video games and vice versa... What differences has it meant for you to work on this type of project, in which, in most cases, large animation studios are involved?

TM: All of these are projects where you have to work carefully, so as not to break the image, respecting the visual style of the project. The downside is that I can't remember any particular project right now in which an anime was made based on a video game, because there are very few video game projects adapted into anime; usually, it's the other way around, and I've participated in many projects—it's very hard to recall [laughs].

CJ: We would be honoured if you could tell us a bit about your way of working, your favourite materials and techniques, and whether your extensive experience in digital media such as video games has made you enjoy working in that medium, or if you still prefer traditional methods.

TM: My favourite working method is one in which I can work quietly, without interruptions, without time limits, and without constant supervision, so I can draw freely. Also, in this respect, I like not being asked to produce a specific number of sheets for a project.

As for digital art, I stick with traditional media, since I still don't have the right tools.

Shortly after finishing one drawing, Matsutake began another. In just moments, he is able to have an idea of what he's going to draw and gets straight to work.

CJ: To finish, we would like you to tell us a bit about your future projects, Mr. Matsutake.

TM: I have recently worked on the third *Psycho-Pass* movie —*Sinners of the System*— and I am currently working on the *Psycho-Pass* anime [Matsutake refers to the third season of the anime, which was in production at the time of this interview] for Production I.G.

There's also the anime *Bokutachi wa Benkyou ga Dekinai* —*We Never Learn*— in which I have participated. I should also say, by the way, that Murcian food is really delicious [laughs].

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For more photographs, visit this link.

Sources

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